

A PROCEDURE TO INVESTIGATE THE COLLAPSE BEHAVIOR OF MASONRY DOMES: SOME MEANINGFUL CASES

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KEYWORDS

Limit analysis, domes, masonry, crack pattern, macro model

ABSTRACT

Masonry domes represent an important feature of the architectural heritage. However, the literature about domes analysis seems less consistent than the one referred to other masonry structures. The collapses happened in recent years as a consequence of seismic actions or lack of maintenance show the need of detailed studies. Here a limit analysis to evaluate the masonry domes behavior is presented. An algorithm based on the kinematic approach has been developed to evaluate the geometric position of the hinges that determine the minimum collapse load multiplier. The proposed procedure is validated by a comparison with some meaningful cases: the collapse of *Anime Sante* Church in L'Aquila, the collapse of *San Nicolò* Cathedral in Noto, the crack pattern of *San Carlo Alle Quattro Fontane* Church in Rome and the analysis developed on *Hagia Sofia* in Istanbul. The comparison with real cases shows a good agreement between the model results and the phenomenological crack patterns.

1. WHY IS IMPORTANT TO STUDY MASONRY DOMES?

The conservation of the cultural heritage is a challenge for the contemporary society. In recent decades, significant resources have been allocated for the conservation and restoration of the architectural heritage. Historical buildings have been restored, protected and reinforced with the intent to limit the risks of degradation or loss, due to phenomena of structural damage and to external factors such as differential settlements, earthquake effects, etc... The wide diffusion of historic masonry constructions in Italy, Europe and in the Mediterranean area, requires reliable tools for the evaluation of their structural safety.

Referring to the heritage, the problem cannot be limited only to the assessment of the structural safety, both under service loads and at collapse, but it is important to evaluate the response to a series of hazards: variations of boundary conditions (soil settlements, induced for example by works carried out close to the construction or by groundwater level variations), structural configuration (partial demolitions, integrations and modifications, strengthening and seismic retrofitting interventions), loads (due to use variations), materials (material decay due to long-time creep effects, material improvement associated to strengthening interventions) and natural hazards (earthquake, wind).

Masonry domes represent a characteristic feature of the European architectural heritage. However, despite of the many efforts done to protect the historical architectural heritage, during last 30 years, several collapses of masonry domes occurred in Mediterranean area, as a consequence of seismic actions or lack of maintenance.

For instances, the dome of Noto Cathedral, in south-east Sicily, collapsed in 1996 as a consequence of the earthquake of 1990 (Binda et al., 2003; Tringali, 2003) and, more recently, the dome of Anime Sante Church collapsed after the earthquake that hit the city of L'Aquila in 2009. Earthquakes have always been a major factor of hazard for this typology of structure, as shown by the vicissitudes of Hagia Sophia in Istanbul (Mainstone, 1988; Hidaka *et al.*, 1993; Sato *et al.*, 1996), whose dome has been damaged and rebuilt many times during its life, as a consequence of seismic events.

Regardless the damages caused by earthquakes, it is common to observe cracking in masonry domes. While vertical cracks, usually, do not provide problems of stability – for instances the dome of *Santa Maria del Fiore* Cathedral in Firenze has been designed by Brunelleschi taking into account the possibility of vertical cracking (Bartoli *et al.*,1996) – instead, horizontal cracks may be a clue of the presence of a possible kinematic mechanism. An example is the church of *San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane* in Roma, built by Borromini in the seventeenth Century: the dome shows vertical cracking in the two main axis, the longitudinal and the transversal ones, and horizontal cracks both at the base of the dome and at the base of the lantern (Degni, 2008).

In this paper, some of the domes previously listed have been studied. Those domes have been chosen on the base of geometrical parameters that may typically influence the structural behavior of domes: the shape of the dome – hemispheric or lowered; the plan – circular or elliptical; the presence or not of the lantern; the presence or not of the backfill. The analyses performed have been compared with the actual surveys of the domes: in the case of *Anime Sante* church and Noto cathedral, results have been compared with the surveys taken after the collapse; in the case of *Hagia Sophia* and *San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane*, comparison has been performed with reference to the observed crack pattern.

The masonry domes are very common structures in the monumental buildings present in the historical centers of the European cities. Despite their relevance and their vulnerability, masonry domes have not been studied as much as other masonry structures: the collapses happened in recent years show the need of more detailed studies.

2. SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

An accurate modelling of the mechanical behavior of the masonry domes is of fundamental importance to assess their structural safety, hence, to ensure their conservation. A dome is a vaulted structure with a circular plan and, usually, with the form of a portion of sphere. Geometrically speaking, a dome is a surface that can be divided into a series of wedges, joined by parallel bands. The meridional forces act along the wedges and are always compressive under vertical loads, while hoop forces, which are perpendicular to the meridional ones, act along the parallel bands. The hoop forces

play the role of restrain the out-of-plane movement of the wedges. They are compressive forces in the upper zone of the dome, while become tensile forces in the lower zone. In most cases, the passage from compressive to tensile forces occurs between 45 and 60 degrees respect to the vertical axis (Heymann, 1982; Como, 2010; Lucchesi, 2007), as shown in figure 1, that reports results obtained by membrane analysis of a semi-circular masonry dome (Pavlovic, 2013).

Therefore, the load bearing capacity of masonry domes is related to their shape: a dome is a double-curved shell that, thanks to its shape, exhibits an optimal structural behavior under axial-symmetric loads. However, in case of masonry domes this “*shape effect*” is affected by the low tensile resistance of masonry material. When the stresses due to self-weight and dead loads exceed the weak tensile strength of masonry, first damages occur: vertical cracks open at the base of dome due to the hoop forces, it may suggest an enlargement of the drum. As a consequence of the development of vertical cracks, the dome is divided in wedges: membrane stresses become compressive stresses and the dome starts behaving like a series of concentric masonry arches along the meridians. This phenomenon is quite common in masonry domes and it does not compromise their structural behavior (Heymann, 1967; Como, 2010; Palmisano, 2014). Instead horizontal cracks, which are due to meridian forces, are more dangerous and may denounce the development of a kinematic mechanism that may lead to collapse. In fact, like in a simple masonry arch, the position of the line of thrust changes, moving from the center of the section to its hedges. When it comes out from the core of the section, the opposite side of the section is not more compressed and should transmit tensile stress, which is not allowed for masonry material. When the line of thrust touches the external or internal surface of the dome a mechanism starts: in that point a hinge develops while in the opposite side a crack opens. This kind of structure is basically designed to bear vertical dead and gravity loads only (Milankovitch, 1907; Heymann, 1969, 1967 and 1977; Focce, 2007). For this reason masonry vaults are vulnerable to seismic actions, as enlightened in the previous section.

Although the construction of masonry domes dates back to the past, most of the domes were built before the seventeenth century, the most important studies on domes were made only starting from the eighteenth century. At that period, project was concerned at the definition of geometric and material characteristics. In 1773 Coulomb has shifted the problem from the planning of the structure to

its static verification and he also introduced the concept of the friction in the mechanics of masonry structures. Thus, many following studies – Navier, Fontana, De La Hire – were developed in the same way, taking into account the friction in equilibrium questions. Many researchers were aimed at the choice of the mechanisms in agreement with the experiments conducted on various geometries of arches. Anyway, the most important structural analysis of dome made in the past is the study made by Poleni (1743) on the dome of the Basilica di San Pietro in Rome. The method proposed by Poleni to assess the stability of the San Pietro's dome – that was cracked along the meridians from the base to the lantern – was inspired by the Hooke's law and it can be considered as a first limited formulation of the static theorem of limit analysis of masonry structures (Como, 2010). A complete overview of the historical approaches to the study of arch and domes and the evolution of the structural theories may be found in Kurrer (2008).

In the first half of the twentieth century, new methods of analysis for the evaluation of the behavior of masonry arch have been proposed. The most diffused approach to study the stability of masonry arch has been proposed by (Pippard and Ashby, 1936; Pippard, 1948). The method, that consider the arch as a two-hinge arch for which the minimum load is applied to a fixed position, allows determining the exact position of the two additional plastic hinges that take place when the arch start behaving as a four hinges mechanism. This approach was based on the work of Milakovitch, who recognized that the main point of masonry structures concerns the global stability and not the local stress and introduced the line of thrust (Milankovitch, 1907; Foce, 2007), and further extended by (Heyman, 1966, 1967, 1977) whit the enunciation of the safety theorem.

Starting form the second half of the last century the attention to the domes increased: in literature numerous studies concerning the mechanical behavior of masonry domes may be found. Main approaches may be synthetized in simplified models and refined models. Models may be based on the limit analysis (Heymann, 1967), which are more rough but at the same time more immediate, or elastic analysis (Flügge, 1973), but also limit analysis, taking into account the mechanical properties of masonry material or the three-dimensional behavior of domes (O'Dowyer, 1999).

Simplified models (Heyman, 1966, 1967, 1969, 1982; Oppenheim *et al.*, 1989; Livesley, 1992; Milani *et al.*, 2009a; Milani *et al.*, 2009b; Palmisano, 2014) focus on the collapse of masonry

domes, and are devoted to the definition of possible kinematic mechanism shapes and the evaluation of collapse load at varying loading conditions or shape of masonry domes or other geometrical parameters, such as the curvature of the dome, the presence or not of lantern and its weight, the presence of *oeil-de-boeuf* or other types of opening. The greater part of these studies follows the approach of the limit analysis, in which masonry domes are modelled as kinematic chain of rigid blocks (Gilbert and Melbourne, 1994). As well known, this modelling approach adopts for masonry material the hypotheses of infinite compressive strength, infinite sliding strength and tensile strength equal to zero, but doesn't require other specific mechanical parameters, as recognized by Milankovitch at the beginning of the XX century (Milankovitch, 1907; Foce, 2007) and the safety of the dome is related to its stereotomy, which has a strong influence on the thrust line shape and on the minimum thickness of a stable arch (Makris and Alexakis, 2013), in particular in case of lateral loads (Alexakis and Makris, 2014). Only few studies propose a non-linear analysis of masonry domes (Pesciullesi *et al.*, 1997; Milani and Tralli, 2012).

Other approaches focus on the elastic behavior of masonry domes, providing more refined models, that usually represent the dome through its middle surface, fit to perform three-dimensional membrane analysis. The greater part of these models (Lucchesi *et al.*, 2007) is devoted to the definition of the stresses distribution in parallels and meridians at varying the geometrical shape of masonry dome, the loading or the boundary conditions. Masonry material is modelled as isotropic or orthotropic material depending on the sophistication of modelling approach. In so doing, mechanical parameters of blocks and mortar joints are taken into account. The sensitivity to the arrangement of blocks of the masonry domes mechanical behavior has been widely acknowledged by historic treatises and literature (Alberti, 1989; Choisy, 1883; Nelli, 1753; Docci, 1992) and by more recent works. (Milani and Cecchi, 2013).

As previously said, masonry domes are structures able to bear mainly vertical loads, hence seismic actions is a major factor of risk for their safety. The behavior of domes subjected to lateral loads has been studied by several authors (Oppenheim, 1992; Clemente, 1998; De Luca *et al.*, 2004; Alexakis and Makris, 2014).

The present study aims to propose a simple and fast procedure to provide reliable evaluation of the minimum collapse load multiplier and of the relative mechanism of collapse, finding the position of the hinges. The method is based on the kinematic approach of the limit analysis. The use of a simplified model is justified by the fact that this typology of structure may be damaged or may collapse because of problems due to instability, without involving the strength of the masonry material. The stability of domes may easily be represented by the line of thrust and is basically related to the geometrical distribution of loads instead to the mechanical properties of masonry material, which may not be exactly established. The analysis here performed is in membrane regime, the reference is made to wedge of dome, hence a bi-dimensional analysis may be performed (Oppenheim *et al.*, 1989). This assumption is motivated by the fact that the presence of vertical cracks due to hoop forces is common in masonry domes: segmental domes do not have problem of stability (Heyman, 1977; Como, 2010; Foraboschi, 2004; Blasi *et al.*, 1994). In the case of domes subjected to uniform distributed loads, with rigid boundary conditions and in the absence of differential settlement these assumptions can be considered correct, hence it is possible to consider portion of them.

In the proposed method, domes have been divided in arches having a constant thickness. The difference in term of self-weight between arch and clove is negligible. In fact, comparing an arch having width w_A equal to 1 meter with a clove having the same width w_A of the arch at 37° (*see fig. 2*) the difference in term of volume is about 1% for domes with a thickness of 1/10 of the diameter. Moreover, the position of the center of gravity in the arch is at $0.62 R$ while in the clove is at $0.48 R$ (*see fig. 2*): it implies an in-stabilizing effect that errs on the side of safety. The proposed method is compared with some meaningful cases of collapsed or cracked domes. The idea is to check if the position of the cracks in a masonry dome coincide with the position of the hinges related to the minimum collapse multiplier. To verify this condition, an algorithm has been developed: to define the position of the hinges that correspond to kinematic mechanism activated by the minimum collapse multiplier. The comparison between the results obtained by the limit analysis and both real crack patterns and surveys on some damaged dome allows to validate the procedure.

3. PROCEDURE TO DEFINE MINIMUM LOAD MULTIPLIER FOR LIMIT ANALYSIS

Here a method for the limit analysis based on the kinematic approach of masonry domes is presented. The proposed method has been compared with some meaningful cases of collapsed or cracked domes in order to verify its reliability. The aim is to check if the position of the cracks in a masonry dome coincides with the position of the hinges related to the minimum collapse multiplier. Hence, an algorithm has been developed; it allows to define the position of the hinges, along the intrados and the extrados, generated by a kinematic mechanism that may be activated by the minimum collapse multiplier.

3.1 GENERAL CASE

The proposed method was developed considering the section of a generic monocentric masonry dome loaded by a lantern, which weight is schematized by two symmetrical forces F_1 and F_2 equal to each other, like shown in Fig.3. For the activation of a mechanism is necessary the formation of 4 hinges. Two hinges $(X_2; Y_2)$ and $(X_4; Y_4)$ are considered fixed and the last one is supposed to be at the base of the dome, which is typical of masonry arches; the another one $(X_2; Y_2)$ is supposed to be matching the lantern. These fixed hinges are supposed to be on extrados. The position of the other two hinges $(X_1; Y_1)$ and $(X_3; Y_3)$ is considered variable along the intrados. As shown in fig. 2a, for both of them the supposed rotation is of about 70° , from the base of the dome to lantern (α_0) and from the lantern to the base (α_3). Each range has been subdivided in some significant portions and for every part have been calculated the geometric center, the weight and the polar coordinates of the hinges. The area of every portion has been calculated like the portion of an annulus which lower and upper arches are in function of variable angles α_0 and α_3 . When the mechanism is activate the interested portions (A_1 , A_2 and A_3) lose their connection and the structure collapse (see Fig.4 b).

The angle α_0 defines the portion of the dome that is not interested in the mechanism, while the A_1 is defined by the angle encompassed between α_0 and α_2 . The right part of the structure is subdivided

in two portions A_2 and A_3 defined by the angle α_3 and, respectively, α_2 and α_4 . The weight of every portion is schematized by a single force applied on the center $G_i (X_{G_i}; Y_{G_i})$ where $i = 1, 3$.

The proposed algorithm allows to define the minimum collapse multiplier in function of variable angles α_0 and α_3 . In the Table 1 is presented an application of it, regarding the geometry, presented in fig.3. The minimum collapse multiplier $\lambda_{C(\alpha_0, \alpha_3)}$, which represents the minimal horizontal force that determines the structural collapse, has been calculated in function of the variable angles α_0 and α_3 that determine not only the position of the hinges $(X_1; Y_1)$ and $(X_3; Y_3)$, but also the areas of arch portion. Each variation covers an angle from the base of the dome to the altitude of the lantern. For the left side the variation is represent by the angle α_0 , while for the right side it's schematized by the angle α_3 . The necessary condition that guarantees the minimum collapse multiplier is in function of the combination of the two angles which must respect these conditions:

$$0 < \alpha_0 < \alpha_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_2 < \alpha_3 < \alpha_4$$

$$\lambda_{C(\alpha_0, \alpha_3)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i \cdot \eta_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n F_i \cdot \eta F_i} \quad (1)$$

where P_i is the self-loads (P_i) that represents every portion encompassed between two hinges and displacement of kinematic chain (η_i). See fig.3.

The weights of the portion of arch were calculated by:

$$P_i = A_i \cdot \gamma \quad (2)$$

where γ is the specific weight and A_i represents the area of the considered annulus. Each portion is in function of angle α_i , internal (r) and external (R) radius, while (b) and (H) are dimensions of the rectangular portion where present (i.e. an elliptic dome has a vertical part on the minor axe. See fig.3).

$$A_i = \frac{R \cdot \alpha_i + r \cdot \alpha_i}{2} \cdot (R - r) + b \cdot H \quad (3)$$

Also the positions of different centers depend of the considered portion and of the angle encompassed between two hinges. It is given by:

$$X_{G_i} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{R^3 - r^3}{R^2 - r^2} \cdot \frac{\sin \frac{\alpha_i}{2}}{\alpha_i} \cdot \cos \frac{\alpha_i}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$Y_{G_i} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{R^3 - r^3}{R^2 - r^2} \cdot \frac{\sin \frac{\alpha_i}{2}}{\alpha_i} \cdot \sin \frac{\alpha_i}{2} + \frac{H}{2} \quad (5)$$

The relative position of **centers** are necessary for the evaluation of the displacements (η_i), but also the position of the hinges is required. The rotation (φ_l) is considered unitary, thus:

$$\eta_{1_i} = \varphi_1 \cdot (X_{G_{1_i}} - X_{1_i}) \quad (6)$$

$$\eta_{2_i} = \varphi_1 \cdot \left(\frac{X_2 - X_{1_i}}{X_{2_{ass_i}} - X_2} \right) \cdot (X_{G_{2_i}} - X_{2_{ass_i}}) \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{3_i} = -\varphi_1 \cdot \left(\frac{X_2 - X_{1_i}}{X_{2_{ass_i}} - X_2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{X_{3_i} - X_{2_{ass_i}}}{X_4 - X_{3_i}} \right) \cdot (X_{G_3} - X_4) \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{F_i} = -\varphi_1 \cdot (X_F - X_{1_i}) \quad (9)$$

$$X_{2_{ass_i}} = \frac{(X_4 - X_{3_i}) \cdot [X_{1_i} \cdot (Y_2 - Y_{1_i}) + (Y_{3_i} - Y_{1_i}) \cdot (X_2 - X_{1_i})] - X_{3_i} \cdot (Y_4 - Y_{3_i}) \cdot (X_2 - X_{1_i})}{(Y_2 - Y_{1_i}) \cdot (X_4 - X_{3_i}) - (Y_4 - X_{3_i}) \cdot (X_2 - X_{1_i})} \quad (10)$$

$$Y_{2_{ass_i}} = Y_1 \cdot \left(\frac{Y_2 - Y_{1_i}}{X_2 - X_{1_i}} \right) \cdot (X_{2_{ass_i}} - X_{1_i}) \quad (11)$$

The generic position of the hinges at intrados is obtained by:

$$X_i = \pm r \cdot \cos \alpha_i \quad (12)$$

$$Y_i = r \cdot \sin \alpha_i + H \quad (13)$$

For this generic example, represented in Fig.3, the minimum collapse multiplier $\lambda_{C(a0, a3)}$ is equal to 3.632; the combination of angles of the relative kinematic mechanism are reported in table 2.

3.2 SPECIFIC CASES

The general procedure proposed may be particularized for specific cases: i.e., in the case of hemispheric domes (see Fig.5a), the term H has zero value. The forces F_1 and F_2 represent the load of the lantern. Their variation produces different values of the collapse multiplier but don't vary the position of the hinges. This means that the position of the hinges is determined by the geometry and not by the loads, while the horizontal force which determines the collapse is in function of the loads itself. For this geometric configuration the minimum collapse multiplier $\lambda_{C(\alpha_0, \alpha_3)}$ is equal to 1.113; the combination of angles of the relative kinematic mechanism are reported in table 2.

On the same way is also possible to analyze the kinematic configuration of a hemispheric dome without the lantern (see Fig.5b), or an arch, on which is applied only a single force F with the aim to simulate an eccentric load condition, instead of two like in the previous case. For this geometric configuration the minimum collapse multiplier $\lambda_{C(\alpha_0, \alpha_3)}$ is equal to 0.186; the combination of angles of the relative kinematic mechanism are reported in table 2.

3.3 CONCLUDING REMARK OF GENERAL PROCEDURE

After the calculation of the minimum collapse multipliers regarding the showed structures (Fig.3, Fig.5a-b) the results are compared in order to study the variation of the collapse multiplier and its relative variation.

The Fig.6a shows the trend of the coefficients $\lambda_{C(\alpha_0, \alpha_3)}$ in function of variable angle α_0 . The values regarding the generic case, showed in Fig.3, are significantly higher than the other two because the major stability that provides vertical portions at the base and the lantern. This values, like those of Fig. 5a, have a symmetric distribution on the contrary of Fig.5b, in which the hemispheric structure is loaded by an only single force and this determines more instability than the case in Fig.5a.

The Fig. 6b represents the relative variation $\lambda_{C_{min}}/\lambda_{C1F_{min}}$ (where $\lambda_{C_{min}}$ is the minimum collapse multiplier of the figuration showed in fig.3, while $\lambda_{C1F_{min}}$ refers to the minimum collapse multiplier of the fig. 5b) of the three minimum collapse multipliers calculated by the proposed algorithm in function of variable angle α_0 . We can see that the results obtained from the geometry proposed in the Fig.3 are

almost twenty times bigger than those of the structure illustrated in *Fig.5b*, while the configuration of *Fig.5a* has a value six times than *Fig.5b*. This means that the major stability in a vaulted structure is ensured by the presence of a symmetric load (*Fig.5a*) and also by the presence of vertical structures at the base which allows to raise the center of gravity (*Fig.3*).

4 SOME MEANINGFUL CASES

In this paragraph the proposed method is validated by a comparison with some meaningful cases: the map of cracks of San Carlo Alle Quattro Fontane Church in Rome, the post-collapse configuration of San Nicolò Cathedral in Noto, the post-collapse configuration of Anime Sante Church in L'Aquila, and the survey analysis made on Hagia Sofia in Istanbul. The comparison with real cases show the reliability of the method.

4.1 SAN CARLO ALLE QUATTRO FONTANE

The church of *San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane* has been planned by Borromini in Roma during the 17th Century and is one of the most famous example of Roman Baroque. The church is based on a stretched central octagonal plant flanked by lateral chapels. Several restoration work have been carried out on the whole complex during its life, but the most significant were completed only in the early 2000 (Degni, 2008). At the end of 1980's the church and the monastery were in bad state of conservation, in particular the dome showed vertical cracking in the two main axis, as shown by the survey carried out by Botta and taken from Degni (2008) reported in *Fig.7*.

While those cracks are typical of the masonry domes, we can observe that horizontal cracks, which characterizes kinematic mechanism, are located at the base of the dome and at the base of the lantern. Hence in the analysis two of the four hinges have been positioned in correspondence of the existing horizontal cracks, while the position of the other two hinges that develop the four hinges mechanism activated by the minimum collapse multiplier have been calculated by the proposed algorithm: they show the possible position of horizontal cracks in case of earthquake. Two models of the dome have been realized along the two main axis, because, due to the elliptic shape of the base of

the dome, radius and weights are different in the longitudinal and cross sections. The weight of the lantern has been schematized by two symmetric equal forces F_1 and F_2 .

The collapse multipliers calculated along the two main axis are quite similar but not equal and so the position of the hinges are. This is due to the different angles between the base of the dome to the lantern. The minimum collapse multiplier λ_{c_i} obtained along the cross section is equal to 0.553, while on the longitudinal section λ_{c_i} is equal to 3.623; the angles related to the two minimum collapse multipliers are reported in Table 3. Fig.7 shows the two models and the kinematic mechanisms, the results obtained are compared in Fig. 8.

4.2 SAN NICOLÒ CATHEDRAL

The construction of the Noto Cathedral dates back to the 1693. The original project developed by Gagliardi was modified in 1770 after the collapse of the first dome, which occurred due to the leak terrain strength. The reconstruction was entrusted to the architect Stefano Ittar in 1789, but also this project has not been completed because of the earthquake of 1848. The project was modified again and the dome was rebuilt for the 3rd time. During the 1950's the Cathedral was restored: maintenance operations have been carried out both on the main vertical and horizontal structures, the wooden floor has been substituted by a new one in pre-stressed concrete and the cracks of the main pillars were filled by gypsum mortar injections (Tringali, 2003). On December 13th 1990 an important earthquake hit the city of Noto: even at the moment seemed that the entity of the earthquake was insufficient to procure serious damages to the San Nicolò Cathedral, it can be stated that it was the beginning of a series of phenomena of instability that led to the collapse of the dome on March 13th 1996. The collapse is certainly to be attributed to a number of weaknesses and injuries suffered by the structures as a consequence of the earthquake of 1990, but also the low quality of the masonry material and presence of the pre-stressed concrete slab was crucial in the collapse of the dome (Binda et al., 2003). In fact, the heavy loads of the concrete slab were transmitted to the pillars – which have been partially damaged during the earthquake – leading to their collapse that involved parts of the roof of the dome (Como, 2010). The conservation state of the Cathedral after the collapse is reported in Fig.9a.

The analysis performed shows a good agreement between the kinematic mechanism of collapse obtained and the damages occurred during the collapse (see Fig.9b). It is possible to observe that the damages interested a big portion of the dome (bigger than the Anime Sante collapse), probably due to the incompatibility of the materials: when the earthquake occurred the concrete slab had a different structural behavior than the other masonry structures and it produced horizontal forces at the base of the dome. In the analysis a hinge has been assumed in correspondence of that point. The minimum collapse multiplier and the angles that determine the position of the hinges of the relative mechanism – reported in Table 3 – are compatible with the real situation.

4.3 ANIME SANTE CHURCH

The construction of the Anime Sante Church begun in 1713 to commemorate the victims of the earthquake that destroyed the city of L'Aquila in 1703. The church consists of a rectangular hall with a barrel vault flanked by two chapels on each side, with eight windows placed to illuminate the presbytery from the hemispherical dome. On April the 6th 2009 an earthquake of $M_w = 6.3$ ($M_L = 5.8$) hit L'Aquila and dozens of villages along the Aterno valley. The earthquake caused 308 victims and seriously damaged the historic center of L'Aquila. The Anime Sante Church had the same destiny: the earthquake provoked diffused cracks of the key stone arches, detachment of the façade and apse, shear cracking of several walls and the collapse of the lantern and of the dome (see Fig.11b)

The analysis has been performed considering the hemispheric portion of the dome loaded by two equal symmetric forces F_1 and F_2 to simulate the lantern. The lowest collapse multiplier λ_{c_i} is equal to 0.077 and is provided by the kinematic chain illustrated in Fig.10. The mechanism of collapse is shown in Fig.11b, together with a modal analysis performed by means of Finite Element in membrane regime (Fig.11a). The first natural frequency corresponds to a local mode of vibration of the lantern, hence, during the seism, stresses were concentrated at the base of it leading to a local mechanism that caused the collapse of the lantern itself. Looking at the surveys carried out after the earthquake (see Fig.11b) it clearly appears that the lantern was the first element that collapsed

dragging a portion of the dome: the results of the limit analysis are in good agreement with it, as shown in Fig.11.

A further limit analysis has been performed taking into account the backfill at the base of dome, which provides a stabilizing effect (Reccia *et al.*, 2014). The analysis has been performed starting from the results obtained without backfill: the combination of angles that provides the minimum collapse multiplier has been used to calculate the variation of the minimum collapse multiplier considering the backfill. Once determined geometry, weight (P_{i_rin}) and barycenter (X_{G_rini} ; Y_{G_rini}) of the backfill, the relative horizontal (δ_{rini}) and vertical (η_{rini}) shifts have been calculated in order to find the minimum collapse multiplier (see Fig.12). The collapse multiplier obtained considering the backfill is significantly bigger than the previous: $\lambda_{C_rin} = 0.302$, hence the backfill provide an increase of stability equal to about 23%, as shown in Fig.13, where results are compared; the values of multipliers and angles are reported in Table 3.

4.4 HAGIA SOFIA

Hagia Sophia was originally built in the fourth Century under Constantine, but soon after was totally destroyed by an earthquake. In the sixth Century it was rebuilt by Emperor Justinian but collapsed again during another earthquake in 558. The dome was then rebuilt in the 562 with a greater high (Mainstone, 1988), giving Hagia Sofia the actual configuration (apart from the minarets made in the sixteenth Century when it was transformed into a mosque). Afterwards, in the course of its history, several collapses occurred, with different reconstructions: the western arch was damaged during the earthquake of 869, while the western part of the dome collapsed during that of the 989. The earthquake of 1346 provoked a further collapse of the dome, damaging about one-third of the area opposite to the one that collapsed of the 989. The reconstruction of this portion (see Fig.14), which ended a few years later, still shows the discontinuity between the reconstructed area and the pre-existing. In the following centuries did not happen further collapses, however the dome is weakened by the lack of homogeneity between the three portions which is constituted by and by the strong irregularities in the whole geometry (Hidaka *et al.*, 1993; Sato *et al.*, 1996).

The structure of the church is complex. The great dome, 34 m of diameter, is supported by a system of four pillars and six arches: it was the first example in which were used the so called *pendentives* to join the rectangular base to the hemispheric dome. The stability of the dome is ensured by two different structural system: in the longitudinal section (East - West) there are two semi-domes that contrast the weight and the thrust of the dome, while in the cross section (North-South) the same task is given by a system of buttresses, which produce a passive way of stability (see Fig.15).

The analysis has been carried out on the base of the surveys and studies of Mainstone (1988): both the original and the rebuilt domes have been analyzed. Fig.16 shows the mechanisms of collapse of the original dome. The comparison between the two configuration shows that the rebuilt dome has a greater stability than the original one (Fig.18). It is also possible to notice that the first hinge coincide with the existing buttress at the base of the dome, that should provide an increase of stability. For this reason, a further analysis of the two domes has been performed taking into account them. Similarly to what previously done in the analysis of Anime Sante, the geometry, weight (P_{i_rin}) and barycenter (X_{G_rini} ; Y_{G_rini}) of the buttress, the relative horizontal (δ_{rini}) and vertical (η_{rini}) shifts have been calculated in order to find the minimum collapse multiplier (see Fig.17). Also in this case, the collapse multipliers obtained considering the backfill are significantly bigger than the previous ones, as shown in Fig.18. This means that the buttress' guarantee a major stability of the whole structure, even if they're made of different material because the stability is insured by the position of the center of gravity. The results are compared in Fig.18, the values of multipliers and angles are reported in Table 3.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Limit kinematic analysis may be a reliable procedure to investigate the behavior at failure of historical masonry domes. The algorithm here presented provides a fast and reliable estimations of collapse multiplier and mechanism of collapse, as demonstrated by the comparison with some meaningful real cases. The analyses conducted in this work, if considered synoptically, allow to outline the following remarks on the cases of study analyzed:

- 2D analyses are suitable to evaluate the collapse behavior of masonry domes, the 3D effect may be neglected for the evaluation of the minimum collapse multiplier. However, when needed, 2D limit analysis may be coupled with more complex analysis able to take into account the mechanical characteristics of materials and the 3D effect.
- The lantern is an essential element of masonry dome, which play an important role in the structural behavior of domes.
- Backfill and buttress increase the stability of masonry domes.

The conservation of masonry dome may be improved thanks to a fast and reliable tool of analysis such as the algorithm here presented, if combined with proper engineering reasoning.

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Paper UARC-2014-0979 revised version, modifications highlighted

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	α_0	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	X_1	Y_1	X_2	Y_2	X_3	Y_3	X_4	Y_4
0	0.000	1.238	1.903	α_2	π	-5.960	2.630	2.248	9.133	1.944	8.264	6.880	2.630
1	0.124			2.027		-5.914	3.367			2.626	7.980		
2	0.248			2.151		-5.778	4.093			3.267	7.615		
3	0.372			2.275		-5.552	4.796			3.859	7.172		
4	0.496			2.399		-5.242	5.466			4.391	6.660		
5	0.620			2.523		-4.851	6.093			4.856	6.086		
6	0.744			2.647		-4.385	6.666			5.246	5.459		
7	0.868			2.771		-3.852	7.178			5.555	4.789		
8	0.992			2.895		-3.26	7.619			5.780	4.085		
9	1.116			3.019		-2.618	7.984			5.915	3.359		
10	α_1		α_4		-1.947	8.263			5.960	2.630			

	X_{G1}	Y_{G1}	X_{G2}	Y_{G2}	X_{G3}	Y_{G3}	X_{2ass}	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_{F1}	η_{F2}	λ_c
0	-4.910	6.128	0	2.630	4.908	4.814	1.619	-1.05	21.146	-1.693	-3.712	-8.204	-0.837
1	-4.742	6.473	2.468	8.564	5.180	4.543	1.903	-1.172	-13.393	-6.841	-3.667	-8.158	-2.768
2	-4.545	6.805	2.826	8.389	5.430	4.248	2.192	-1.233	-91.933	-62.617	-3.53	-8.021	-23.656
3	-4.319	7.122	3.167	8.185	5.656	3.931	2.472	-1.233	24.179	19.544	-3.305	-7.796	7.249
4	-4.067	7.421	3.489	7.954	5.856	3.595	2.721	-1.175	12.166	10.874	-2.994	-7.486	4.135
5	-3.789	7.700	3.791	7.698	6.029	3.241	2.906	-1.062	9.535	8.839	-2.603	-7.094	3.623
6	-3.488	7.955	4.068	7.419	6.172	2.873	2.969	-0.898	10.11	9.072	-2.138	-6.629	4.268
7	-3.165	8.186	4.321	7.120	6.285	2.493	2.784	-0.687	17.469	14.158	-1.605	-6.096	8.243
8	-2.824	8.390	4.546	6.803	6.366	2.104	2.011	-0.437	-59.073	-41.028	-1.013	-5.504	-32.09
9	-2.466	8.565	4.743	6.470	6.415	1.709	-0.781	-0.152	-8.874	-5.187	-0.37	-4.862	-5.910
10	0	2.630	4.908	6.129	0	1.315	-29.121	-1.947	-4.55	-35.081	0.301	-4.191	-12.912

not variable data
 combination that provides minimum λ_c

Table 1 – Example of algorithm's calculation

	α_0	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	λ_c
General case	0.620	1.238	1.903	2.523	3.147	3.623
Hemispheric dome loaded by 2 forces	0.615	1.230	1.911	2.526	3.147	1.113
Hemispheric dome without lantern	0.569	1.222	2.428	3.147	/	0.186

Table 2 – Angles (rad) and minimum collapse multipliers of the different typologies of dome.

	α_0	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	λ_c
San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane: cross section	0.889	1.266	1.875	2.637	3.147	0.553
San Carlo alle Quattro Fontane: longitudinal section	0.620	1.238	1.903	2.523	3.147	3.623
Cathedral of Noto	0.815	1.353	1.789	2.600	3.147	0.149
Anime Sante: without backfill	0.788	1.313	1.827	2.615	3.147	0.077
Anime Sante: with backfill	0.788	1.313	1.827	2.615	3.147	0.302
Hagia Sophia: original dome	0.958	1.222	1.836	2.449	/	0.294
Hagia Sophia: original dome with backfill	0.958	1.222	1.836	2.449	/	1.095
Hagia Sophia: rebuilt dome	0.855	1.222	2.565	3.147	/	1.643
Hagia Sophia: rebuilt dome with backfill	0.855	1.222	2.565	3.147	/	2.317

Table 3 – Angles (rad) and minimum collapse multipliers of the differestudy.